

Carbapenem Resistance Gene in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolates from Duhok, Iraq

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Abstract

This study aimed to molecular investigation of prevalence the carbapenem-resistant gene (blaOXA24) in *P. aeruginosa* in isolates collected from Duhok hospitals in Duhok City, Kurdistan, Iraq. Six hundred and seventy samples (burn, ear, wound, urine, and sputum) were collected from patients who attended the main hospitals in Duhok city during the period from February to July 2024. Bacterial identification and antimicrobial susceptibility were tested using traditional methods and confirmed by the VITEK 2 compact system. Fifty selected *P. aeruginosa* isolates were molecularly detected by conventional PCR assay using a specific primer targeting gene blaOXA24 and also the sequencing of the resistance genes to antibiotics was done. For the prevalence of *P. aeruginosa*, 160 isolates were isolated from 670 samples including, burn 48(7.17%), ear 39(5.82%), wound 25(3.73%), urine 27(4.03%), and sputum 21(3.13%). Regarding antibiotic-resistant patterns, resistance was noticed at 80.6% for meropenem and 73.1% for imipenem. In the molecular study, 50 isolates from 160 were selected for PCR assay. Selected isolates were confirmed by PCR assay. 44/50 (88%) isolates were positive for the blaOXA24 gene with size 246 bp. and have got clear bands on agarose gel 1% and electrophoresis, 10 PCR positive samples were selected to know the sequencing of blaOXA24 gene. Moreover, all sequences were submitted to the National Center for Biotechnology Information blast, recorded into Genbank, and got accession numbers for blaOXA24 (OP600031, OP600042, OP600043, OP600044, OP600045, OP600046, OP600047, OP600048, OP600049, and OP600050). The blaOXA24 samples were identical (98-99%) to reference sequences.

Keywords: blaOXA24, Carbapenem, resistance gene, *P. aeruginosa*, PCR.

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Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic pathogenic bacterium and a causative agent of different nosocomial infections including pneumonia, septicemia, endocarditis, meningitis, and malignant otitis externa. The infection of *P. aeruginosa* is more prevalent in patients with cystic fibrosis, burns, wounds, intravenous drug addiction, leukemia, and organ transplants (Ali, 2019). *P. aeruginosa* is a serious issue as it endangers the selection of appropriate treatment, resulting in morbidity and mortality of the infected patients (Obritsch *et al.*, 2004). Resistance of *P. aeruginosa* to several commonly used antibiotics has increased with the emergence of MDR strains which is a matter of great concern (Yayan *et al.*, 2015). The development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria is because of

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the exposure of the pathogen to various antimicrobials, like carbapenems leading to the development of beta-lactamases producing Gram-negative bacteria including *P. aeruginosa* with enhanced antibiotic resistance (Ong *et al.*, 2011). Antimicrobial resistance is one of the most severe global public health threats of this century (El-Banna *et al.*, 2019) and one of the most significant challenges faced by healthcare (IACG, 2019).

P. aeruginosa is highly able to develop natural and acquired drug resistance through various mechanisms, including the production of antibiotic-inactivating enzymes or antibiotic-modifying enzymes, inhibiting the drug's penetration through the cell wall, changing the target of antibacterial action, limiting the drug's ability to reach its target and adaptation to the adverse environment (Pang *et al.*, 2019).

(OXA-type) β -lactamases

They are known as OXA-type beta-lactamases because they have the potential to hydrolyze oxacillin. They have been found in many Gram-negative bacteria. Most frequently in *P. aeruginosa* (Ali 2019), they are divided into four classes: A, B, C, and D. Class A, C, and D enzymes are serine β -lactamases, while class B are metallo-enzymes because they possess one or two zinc ions in their catalytic sites (Benie *et al.*, 2017), and they confer resistance not only to penicillins and cephalosporins but also against carbapenems which are considered the last-resort β -lactam antibiotic therapy (Ruffin, and Brochiero, 2019). Enzymes of this class are serine- β -lactamases poorly inhibited by EDTA or clavulanic acid. These carbapenemases are of the oxacillinase (OXA) enzyme type, and show a weak activity to carbapenems (Mohammed, 2020). These enzymes were originally discovered in clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* in Ankara Turkey (Ali 2019).

The OXA type beta-lactamases found in clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* are OXA-1, OXA-2, OXA-3, OXA-4, OXA-5, OXA-10, OXA-11, OXA-13, OXA-14, OXA-15, OXA-16, OXA-17, OXA-18, OXA-19, OXA-20, OXA-28, OXA-31, OXA-32, OXA-35, OXA-45, OXA-46, OXA-50, OXA-56 and OXA-74 (Ali 2019). The present study highlighted molecular investigation and the prevalence of the carbapenem-resistant gene (blaOXA24) in *P. aeruginosa* in isolates collected from Dhhok hospitals in Duhok City, Kurdistan, Iraq.

Material and Methods

Place and Period of the Study

The study was carried out in the Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Basic Science, College of Nursing, University of Duhok from February to July 2024. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee /Scientific Research Division / Directorate of Planning / Duhok General Health Directorate/ Ministry Of Health/ Kurdistan Regional Government/ Iraq [Reference number: 22062021-6-8].

Bacterial Isolation

This study included 670 samples that were collected from different clinical sources (sputum, ear swab, urine, wound, and burn) in the hospitals (Azadi Teaching Hospital, Hevi Pediatric Teaching Hospital, Burn Hospital, Accident and Emergency Teaching Hospital, and private laboratory) in Duhok city; patients were involved both sexes and different age groups, samples were transported to the Microbiology Laboratory, within 1-2 hrs for culturing, and bacteriological identification. All samples were first cultured using sterile cotton swabs in sterile vials containing Nutrient broth and Amies transport medium swabs that were incubated at 37°C/24 hrs for microbiological identifications. To isolate *P. aeruginosa* each sample was first identified according to general cultural

characteristics of colonies (color, shape, and size) grown on Nutrient agar, Blood agar, and MacConkey agar that were incubated at 37°C for 24hrs for further tests.

Identification of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Bacterial identification was done by using Gram stain, biochemical tests (catalase test, oxidase test, IMViC test, and Triple Sugar Iron test), Ceftrimide agar, and confirmation test was done by using automated VITEK 2 compact system.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test (Kirby Bauer Disk Diffusion Test)

For all identified *P. aeruginosa* isolates, a disc diffusion test for antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed as recommended by the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute CLSI (CLSI, 2020) and the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing EUCAST (EUCAST, 2021) using meropenem 10 µg (MEM) and imipenem 10 µg (IMP). Sterile nutrient broths were prepared and well-isolated colonies of the bacterium growing on a nutrient agar plate were inoculated into it. The broths were incubated at 37°C until the culture equaled 0.5 McFarland standard. A McFarland 0.5 turbidity standard corresponds to an inoculum of 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml. The prepared suspension was used within 15 minutes. A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the inoculum and wiped evenly across the surface of the Muller Hinton agar plate (Okezie *et al.*, 2021). The inoculated plates were placed at room temperature to allow absorption of excess moisture, then the antibiotic discs were placed firmly on the inoculated plates with forceps to ensure contact with the agar, then incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs. After incubation, the diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in mm. and compared with that of the NCCLS (CLSI, 2020).

Molecular Detection

Extraction of DNA

For DNA extraction, the boiling method was performed as described by Levesque and co-workers, by taking two to three fresh colonies from a bacterial plate and mixing them in 800 µl of deionized water. Then placed in a water bath at 100°C for 10 min followed by centrifugation at 1200 rpm for 2 minutes using a micro centrifuge (Mini Spin Plus, Eppendorf). Crude lysate containing DNA was stored at -20°C for use over a long period (Levesque *et al.*, 1995).

Determination of DNA Concentration and Purity

The concentration and purity of the DNA of each isolate were determined using a Nanodrop machine (Molecular Department, General Central Laboratory, General Health Directorate in Duhok). Confirmation of the quantity and purity of the DNA was calculated by the Nanodrop 2000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific Germany). The purity of the DNA was judged based on an optical density ratio of 1.7-1.8 and a concentration between 10-50 nanog /µl.

Primers used in the Detection of *P. aeruginosa*

The Forward and Reverse primers were prepared as a stock solution by dissolving the freeze-dried powder in double distilled and deionized H₂O to the concentration of 100 pmol /µl, the working solution of the Forward and Reverse primers was 10 pmol/µl.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

The PCR analysis was done in the Molecular Genetics Laboratory/Animal Resources Department / Agricultural Engineering Sciences College/Salahalddin University. This analysis was conducted to confirm the identification of *P. aeruginosa* and detect some resistance genes of *P. aeruginosa* isolated from different clinical samples.

PCR Components

The PCR reaction was performed in a final volume (25 μ l) which consisted of 12.5 μ l PCR Master Red load Taq Master (2X) (AMPLIQON, Denmark) which contains 0.4 mM of each deoxynucleoside triphosphate (dNTP), 3 mM MgCl₂, PCR Buffer (150Mm Tris-HCL, pH8.5, 0.2%Tween20), 0.2 units/ μ L Taq DNA polymerase and red dye.10 pmol/ μ l of each primer and 50-100 ng genomic DNA. The concentration and quantity of components used in the PCR reaction are summarized in (Table 1).

Table 1. PCR Components

No.	Components	Concentration	Volume
1.	Master Mix	2 X	12.5 μ l
2.	Forward primer	10 pmol/ μ l	1 μ l
3.	Reverse primer	10 pmol/ μ l	1 μ l
4.	DNase free water	-	8.5 μ l
5.	DNA template	50 nanog / μ l	2 μ l
Total			25 μ l

Source: Jawher and Hassan, 2022)

The conventional PCR machine is set up with many cycles and different temperatures for each step, including step one, Initial denaturation. Followed by step two (denaturation, annealing, and Extension), finally an extra extension. PCR program for blaOXA-24 gene, is summarized in Table (2).

Table 2. Steps of Thermal Cycling, (PCR Program) for Gene blaOXA-24

Steps	Temp°C	Time	No. of cycles
Initial denaturation	94°C	3 min	1
Denaturation	94°C	30 sec	35
Annealing	52°C	1 min	
Extension	72°C	2 min	
Final extension	72°C	6 min	1

Source: Nitz et al., 2021

Detection of Amplified Products and Extracted DNA Using Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

The agarose gel of 1% concentration was utilized to confirm the size of genomic DNA bands and to confirm the size of the PCR products. Agarose gel consisted of 1g of agarose powder dissolved in 100ml of 1X TBE buffer using a microwave. After agarose solution cooled down to 45-50°C, 6 μ l of 10 μ g/ml of Ethidium bromide was added. Then, the solution was poured into the gel tank with the combs in place and left to cool for 30 minutes. The combs were removed carefully and the tank was placed in the electrophoresis system containing running buffer consisting of 1X TBE, the buffer was poured until it covered the gel for about 2-3mm. The PCR sample (6 μ l) is to be electrophoresed and pipetted into wells within the gel. DNA ladder (1500- 100 bp) was carefully pipetted into a separate well in the gel. The DNA was electrophoresed at 50-100V until the DNA fragments were separated according to their size. The resulting DNA fragments were visualized using a UV trans illuminator at 302 nm and photographed by using a digital camera (Bio-Rad, Molecular Imager®, ChemiDoc™XRS+with ImageLab™Software) (Mohammed, 2020).

DNA Sequencing

After DNA extraction from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates, ten bacterial isolates were selected to perform DNA sequencing by sending the PCR products of the ten samples with the blaOXA24 primer to Macrogen biotechnology company (Korea), to know the sequence of the genes using ABI 3130 genetic analyzer ((ABI PRISM® BigDye™ Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kits (Applied Biosystem)). The gene sequences for bacterial isolates were applied to the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) which is a searching tool that applies the sequence alignment method and is available at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) website, and the bacterial isolates were recorded into GenBank data.

Statistical Analysis

All data statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 20 (IBM USA).

Result

A total of 670 different clinical samples from (burn, wound, ear, urine, and sputum) were aseptically collected from patients. The samples were screened for isolation of *P. aeruginosa*. There were 160 isolates of *P. aeruginosa* (23.88%), while 510 (76.12%) showed no bacterial growth

The highest expression of *P. aeruginosa* was among the samples of burn and ear swabs (7.17% and 5.82%, respectively), followed by urine (4.03%), and wound (3.73%), while the lowest rate was in sputum swabs (Table 3).

Table 3. Isolates of *P. aeruginosa* from Different Clinical Samples

Sources	Number of samples (%)	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
Burn	120 (17.9%)	48 (7.17%)	72 (10.75%)
Ear	131 (19.6%)	39 (5.82%)	92 (13.73%)
Wound	142 (21.2%)	25 (3.73%)	117(17.46%)
Urine	220 (32.8%)	27 (4.03%)	193 (28.81%)
Sputum	57 (8.5%)	21(3.13%)	36 (5.37%)
Total	670 (100%)	160 (23.88%)	510 (76.12%)

Table 4 showed the rates of antibiotic resistance in total *P. aeruginosa* isolates, the resistance was 80.6% for meropenem. Imipenem gave a resistance of 73.1% (Table).

Table 4. Rates of Antibiotic Resistance in Total *P. aeruginosa* Isolates

Antibiotics	Symbol	Disc potency (µg)	No. (%)
Meropenem	MEM	10	129 (80.6%)
Imipenem	IPM	10	117 (73.1%)

For the distribution of blaOXA24 gene, Out of the 160 *P. aeruginosa* isolates, 50 isolates were studied and selected for PCR. The blaOXA24 gene was detected in 44/50 (88%) isolates (Figures 1).

Figure 1. PCR Product of blaOXA24 (246 bp) Gene in *P. aeruginosa* Isolates. The Amplification of DNA Appears as a Ladder-Like Pattern where, Lane (M) DNA Marker (100 bp), Lane (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10) Represent Positive Isolates, and Lane (C) Indicate Negative Control without Band

DNA Sequencing Result

During this study, after molecular analysis ten bacterial isolates were sent to MacroGen Biotechnology Company (Korea) for DNA sequencing, and then recorded into Genbank. Each bacterial isolate obtained a separate accession number for blaOXA24 gene (Table 5).

Table 5. The Accession Numbers of *P. aeruginosa* Bacterial Identification Depend on blaOXA 24 Gene Submitted in the GenBan

IsolateNo.	Species name	Accession number
		blaOXA24
1	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600031
2	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600042
3	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600043
4	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600044
5	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600045
6	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600046
7	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600047
8	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600048
9	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600049
10	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600050

On the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) site, after typing the GenBank isolate accession number in the search field, the following information about blaOXA24 for each bacterial isolate (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) (figures 2-11).

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-1 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600031.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to: ▾

LOCUS OP600031 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-1 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
 ACCESSION OP600031
 VERSION OP600031.1
 KEYWORDS .
 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 2. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600031) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-2 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600042.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

LOCUS OP600042 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
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 VERSION OP600042.1
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 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 3. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600042) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-3 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600043.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

[Go to:](#)

LOCUS OP600043 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-3 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
 ACCESSION OP600043
 VERSION OP600043.1
 KEYWORDS .
 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 4. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600043) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-4 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600044.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

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 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-4 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
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 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 5. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600044) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-5 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600045.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

LOCUS OP600045 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-5 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
 ACCESSION OP600045
 VERSION OP600045.1
 KEYWORDS .
 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 6. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600045) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-6 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600046.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

LOCUS OP600046 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-6 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
 ACCESSION OP600046
 VERSION OP600046.1
 KEYWORDS .
 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 7. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600046) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-7 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600047.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

LOCUS OP600047 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
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 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 8. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600047) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-8 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600048.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

Go to:

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 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer, A.T. and Abdulkahar, I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 9. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600048) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-9 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600049.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

[Go to:](#)

LOCUS OP600049 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-9 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
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 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
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 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 10. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600049) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

GenBank ▾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-10 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds

GenBank: OP600050.1
[FASTA](#) [Graphics](#)

[Go to:](#)

LOCUS OP600050 209 bp DNA linear BCT 05-DEC-2022
 DEFINITION Pseudomonas aeruginosa strain A-10 OXA family beta-lactamase (blaOXA) gene, partial cds.
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 SOURCE Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 ORGANISM [Pseudomonas aeruginosa](#)
 Bacteria; Proteobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Pseudomonadales; Pseudomonadaceae; Pseudomonas.
 REFERENCE 1 (bases 1 to 209)
 AUTHORS Monawer,A.T. and Abdulkahar,I.M.
 TITLE Direct Submission
 JOURNAL Submitted (06-OCT-2022) Nursing College, Basic Science Department, Duhok University, Sumel, Duhok, Duhok 38, Iraq
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Figure 11. blaOXA 24 Gene Sample under the Accession Number (OP600050) in (NCBI) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) was Reported as *P. aeruginosa* in Duhok Governorate, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

The DNA sequencing of the blaOXA24 gene that amplified by using PCR that was submitted in GenBank. The BLAST analysis was showed that the blaOXA 24 gene shared 99% homology with the sequences of *P. aeruginosa*. (Table 6).

Table 6. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolates and Genbank Accession Number of blaOXA24 Gene

Isolate No.	Speciesname	AccessionNo.	Similarity %	References AccessionNo.	Country
1	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600031	99	OQ096444	Philippines
2	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600042	98	OQ096445	Philippines
3	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600043			
4	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600044			
5	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600045	98	OQ096446	Philippines
6	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600046			
7	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600047			
8	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600048	98	OQ096447	Philippines
9	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600049			
10	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	OP600050			

Discussion

In the current study, out of 670 clinical samples that were obtained and collected from patients, 160 (23.88%) isolates of *P. aeruginosa* were detected and identified, this result is similar to a previous studies (Causapé *et al.*, 2017; AlSaffar and Jarallah, 2019; Al-Daraghi and Al-Badrwi, 2020; Monawer, 2024).

The frequencies of *P. aeruginosa* isolates were detected at most from burn 48/120 (7.17%), ear samples 39/131(5, 82%), urine 27/220 (4.03%), and followed by wound 25/142 (3.73%), whereas the lowest rate was among sputum samples 21/57(3.13%), This corroborates the work of previous study in Iraq (Monawer, 2024).

For 160 *P. aeruginosa* isolates, imipenem and meropenem showed a resistant rate of (80.6%) and (73.1%), respectively, this result is similar to a previous study In India which indicated that Imipenem (80.77%) was detected to be the most effective antipseudomonal drug (Senthamarai, 2014). Siddiqua *et al.*, found that (76%) and (87%) of the isolates were resistant to meropenem and imipenem, respectively (Siddiqua *et al.*, 2018).

In the current study, gel electrophoresis detected DNA fragments of blaOXA24 on 246 bp in 44/50 (88%) of bacterial strains by PCR assay. One of the most important findings of the current study is the high prevalence of the blaOXA24 gene. These findings were in agreement with a previous study in Indonesia has indicated the prevalence of the blaOXA24 gene among clinical and environmental carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas* was 20 (42%) (Endraputra *et al.*, 2021), and closely similar to an Iraqi study (Monawer, 2024).

Conclusion

From the results of the present study, it was concluded that the majority of *P. aeruginosa* isolates were collected from burn, followed by ear, urine, wound, and sputum swabs, and all *P. aeruginosa* isolates expressed good resistance to meropenem, followed by imipenem. Moreover, highly prevalence of the blaOXA24 resistance gene among *P. aeruginosa* isolates.

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